

SECOND SOUTHERN SCIENCE CONFERENCE

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SCAN ME

November 2024.

Confirmed Speakers (Until March 2024)

Mayná Coutinho is a seasoned Environmental Engineer, currently serving as the Environmental/Sustainability Coordinator (ESG) at Companhia Estadual de Águas e Esgotos (CEDAE) in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Additionally, she holds the prestigious positions of President of the Guandu River Basin Water Committee and President of the State Water Resources Council of Rio de Janeiro, where she has driven significant environmental policy development and management. With a strong academic background, including a Bachelor of Science in Environmental Engineering from Universidade Federal Fluminense and an Associate Degree in Environment from Colégio Federal Pedro II, Mayná has been instrumental in implementing sustainability practices and pioneering environmental projects. Her notable work includes leading the Forest Restoration Programme of Tingua-Bocaina, in partnership with the State Government of Rio de Janeiro and The Nature Conservancy Brazil, aimed at reforesting 30,000 hectares in the state's most crucial water supply basin. Complementing her professional endeavors, Mayná is currently enhancing her expertise through online specializations in Climate Solutions at the University of Edinburgh and Sustainable Cities at Johns Hopkins University.

Dr. Miguel Walter Fornes, MD PhD, conducts primary research at the National Research Council of Argentina (CONICET) and the Institute of Histology and Embryology in Mendoza (IHEM). He oversees the Mendoza Andrological Research Laboratory (LIAM), focusing on sperm physiology. The laboratory is committed to unravelling the intricacies of sperm formation and physiology within the seminiferous tubule. Our investigations highlight the significant influence of diet on various parameters such as morphology, spermatid capacitation, and ejaculated sperm count. We particularly explore the effects of dietary fat content, with a keen interest in supplementing unhealthy diets with olive oil. Our research has shown promising results in reversing sperm failure induced by high-fat diets. The LIAM team delves into the underlying mechanisms, both positive and negative, to provide comprehensive insights into sperm health and function.

Bhavna Ambudkar is a seasoned professional with expertise in electronics, telecommunications, research, teaching, entrepreneurship, and innovation. With over 25 years of experience in Electronics & Telecommunication, she excels in Computer Networks, Digital Electronics, Healthcare, Innovation, and Educational Technology. Bhavna holds a Doctor of Science (D.Sc.) degree in Engineering, along with a Ph.D. and Masters in Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering. She has authored over 50 research publications and holds 10 patents, showcasing her ability to bridge academic research with practical applications. In addition to her academic achievements, Bhavna has been instrumental in nurturing entrepreneurship and innovation. She has mentored numerous start-ups and entrepreneurs, facilitating idea development and funding acquisition. Bhavna's contributions have earned her recognition at national and international levels, bolstering her extensive networks and collaborations across various domains. Certified by Cambridge International and Dale Carnegie, she is adept at building and fostering professional relationships. Bhavna's multifaceted expertise and commitment to innovation continue to shape her impactful contributions to academia and industry alike.

Juliana Gracieli Rezende de Oliveira. Graduated in Biological Sciences from de the State University of Montes Claros - UNIMONTES - (2004-2008), Master in Rural Studies from Federal University of Vales do Jequitinhonha and Mucuri - UFMG (2023). Mastering in Professional Master's Degree in National Network in Water Resources Management and Regulation - ProfÁgua (2023). Specialist in Biotechnology from Federal University of Lavras - UFPA (2010). Specialist in Management and Educational Environmental from the Federal University of Maranhão UFMA - (2023). Specializing in Conciliation and Conflict Mediation - Mediator Center (2022). She is currently the owner of the environmental consultancy company, Ipê Environmental Solutions, at Unaí/MG and she has worked with a great focus on managing and mediating conflicts in river basins where there is conflict over the use of water resources through Local Management Committees.

Dr. Fernando Pelegrini holds a degree in Chemical Engineering from the Federal University of Bahia (1981), a specialization in Petrochemical Engineering (CENPEQ-PETROBRAS/UFBA), a specialization in Equilibrium Separation Processes (COFIC / UFBA), a master's degree in Chemical Engineering from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (1987) and a PhD in Chemical Engineering from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro and Lyngby University (Denmark) (1992). He worked at the Federal University of Bahia as a researcher (4 years), at the Camaçari Petrochemical Complex - Bahia (6 years) and at the School of Chemistry of UFRJ for 27 years, where he became a Full Professor. He is currently a Volunteer Professor at EQ/UFRJ and a Full Professor at the SENAI CIMATEC University Center. He was awarded as Researcher 1A (CNPq) and Scientist of the State of Rio de Janeiro. He has about 250 papers published in national and international journals, 600 papers in national and international congresses, and more than 155 students graduated in master's and/or doctoral degrees. Translator of Van Ness (Thermodynamics), Incropera (Mass and Heat Transfer) and Reactor Calculus (Roberts). Coordinator of several projects with companies and government institutions. Coordinator of the Competence Center for Process Intensification at SENAI-CIMATEC. He has experience in the area of Chemical Engineering, with emphasis on Applied Thermodynamics and Process Engineering, working mainly on the following topics: PETROLEUM, PETROCHEMICALS, biofuels, natural products, supercritical fluid, phase balance, intensification and optimization of processes, circular economy and green H₂.

Dr. Nancy F. Ferreyra completed her PhD in 2002, followed by postdoctoral research at various prestigious institutions. She conducted research at the Laboratory of Organic Electrochemistry and Redox Photochemistry of Joseph Fourier University in Grenoble, France, the Laboratory of Biophysical Chemistry and Molecular Oncology at the Institute of Biophysics Brno, Czech Republic, and the Bioelectrochemistry Laboratory of the Faculty of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at the University of Chile, Santiago de Chile. In 2005, she joined the Scientific and Technical Research Council of Argentina, CONICET. Currently, Nancy holds the position of Associate Professor at the Faculty of Chemical Sciences at the University of Córdoba. She also serves as an Independent Researcher at INFIQC-CONICET. Nancy's research focuses on the design, synthesis, characterization, and application of biofunctionalized nanomaterials for the development of electrochemical biosensors.

Dr. Ramon Loureiro Pimenta graduated in Veterinary Medicine from the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ) in 2009, PhD in Science, Technology and Innovation in Agriculture from the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ) in 2018. He has been working in the poultry industry for 14 years, slaughtering, processing and recycling of butcher animals in various industries in Brazil and 6 years as a university professor, currently linked to the Department of Public Health at the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro teaching the subject Poultry Health. Participates as a collaborator in research groups at UFRRJ, Fiocruz and University of Vassouras in the areas of antimicrobial resistance in poultry farming, aquaculture and slaughterhouse effluents. He has been part of the Rio de Janeiro Poultry Health Committee for 6 years, in addition to having carried out several works together with the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply (MAPA) and EMBRAPA.

Dr. Paloma Martins Mendonças Bachelor in Biological Sciences in Universidade Santa Úrsula (2004). Specialist in Medical Entomology from the Oswaldo Cruz Institute - IOC/FIOCRUZ (2006). Training Course in Studies on Muscoid Diptera of Forensic and Public Health Importance, held at the Oswaldo Cruz Institute. Master in Parasitic Biology from the Oswaldo Cruz Institute, Fiocruz. PhD in Veterinary Sciences (Veterinary Parasitology) from UFRRJ where she was a CNPq scholarship holder. He has a Post-Doctorate in Biodiversity and Health at Fundação Oswaldo Cruz (2015-2017), with a scholarship from CNPq. He has experience in the area of Parasitology, with an emphasis on Entomology of Parasites and Vectors and Forensic Entomology, working mainly on the following topics: Bionomy of muscoid dipterans, morphology, scanning electron microscopy, human and animal myiasis, alternative control of arthropods of medical importance-veterinary, molecular taxonomy of muscoid dipterans. She was a scholarship holder of the Bolsa Nota 10-FAPERJ Program from March 2009 to February 2010. She served as Municipal Secretary for the Environment and Urbanism of Itaboraí (2017-2020). She works as an Environmental Consultant at the company Contact Soluções Ambientais. Vice Coordinator of the Professional Master's Degree in Environmental Sciences at the University of Vassouras (04/2021 to 08/2023). Adjunct Professor of the Professional Master's Degree in Environmental Studies at the University of Vassouras. Executive Editor of Revista da Saúde - UV (2017-2024).

André Dantas Martins serves as the Environment Secretary for the Municipal City Hall of Paty do Alferes, leveraging expertise in General Biology with a focus on Environmental Management, Clinical Analysis, Forest Restoration, Recovery of Degraded Areas, Environmental Licensing, Environmental Education, Waste Management, and Conservation Unit Management. With demonstrated experience in public leadership and management, he specializes in Environmental Management of Hydrographic Basins, Environmental Expertise and Audit. Currently pursuing a master's degree in Environmental Sciences at the University of Vassouras, Martins is actively engaged as a member of the Municipal Environmental Council, REBIO ARARAS Advisory Council, and the Executive Board of the Pirabanhas Committee. He also holds the position of President at ANAMMA-RJ.

Daniela Alejandra Quinteros is a pharmacist with a Ph.D. in chemical sciences from the National University of Córdoba (UNC), Argentina. She is currently an Adjunct Professor (by competition) at the same University and an Independent researcher at the National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET). She completed her postdoctoral study at the Complutense University - Madrid (2010), Bioforge (Biomaterials, Biomimetics, Nanobiotechnology) - Universidad De Valladolid - Spain - 2013 and University of Campinas - Brasil - 2018. Her research project is related to the development of pharmaceutical systems for the improvement of pharmacotherapy of pathologies of high prevalence, on this opportunity, we focused in for the treatment of neurodegenerative eye pathologies. She has expertise in neuroprotective pharmaceutical systems applied topically and intravitreally in different models in vivo to improve ocular pharmacotherapy. Within this framework, She has directed master's degrees, doctoral theses, and postdoctoral fellows. In addition, has received awards from The Association for Research in Vision Ophthalmology, the Ministry of Industry and Mining of the province of Córdoba, and awards in congresses. Has published 30 scientific articles in journals 6 book chapters, and is the author of 1 Invention Patent. She is a full member of the Argentine Society of Experimental Pharmacology (AAFE), part of the CONICET-CCT-CORDOBA, is a member of the board of directors of the Institute Research and Development in Pharmaceutical Technology (UNITEFA) and co-founder of 3DFarmic.

Ana Karine Furtado de Carvalho is a Food Engineer graduated from the Federal University of Ceará-Brazil (UFC) and earned both a master's and doctoral degree from the Graduate Program in Chemical Engineering at the Lorena School of Engineering - University of São Paulo-Brazil (EEL-USP). Specialized in Bioprocesses, renewable energy matrix development, and biosystems, contributes to projects of biorefinery systems. With expertise in chemical reactors and bioreactors, the professional also works on the reuse of agro-industrial waste for fine chemistry and material characterization. Currently serving as a faculty member at the University of São Paulo in the Department of Basic and Environmental Sciences at EEL-USP, the engineer continues to make significant contributions to the field of Engineering.

Paulo Wilton Camara is a highly accomplished academic and professional with extensive experience in various fields. He holds a Post-Doctorate in Military Sciences and a Doctorate in Political Science, among other degrees. With over 33 years of experience in teaching and academic management, he has worked in multiple institutions in Rio de Janeiro and Goiás. Throughout his career, he has been involved in creating and managing educational programs, such as the Soma Business Incubator. He currently holds several leadership positions at the University of Vassouras, including General Coordinator of Postgraduate Studies and Deputy Coordinator of the Master's Degree in Environmental Sciences. Additionally, he is actively involved in research projects related to renewable energy, environmental monitoring, and circular economy. In the business realm, he founded PW/TARGET Consulting and Services Ltd., specializing in strategic business management and innovation. He is also a member of professional associations and has served as a consultant and instructor for organizations like Sebrae/RJ. With expertise in public policy, planning, sales, marketing, operations, and logistics, Paulo Wilton Camara is a respected figure in academia and business, contributing significantly to both fields.

Ernesto García graduated in Industrial Engineering from the Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana - Azcapotzalco (UAM-A), obtained a Master's degree in Manufacturing Engineering with a specialization in control and automation from the Escuela Superior de Ingeniería Mecánica y Eléctrica - Azcapotzalco (SEP-ESIME Azc), and completed a Doctorate in the Science of Mechanical Engineering with a specialization in Tribology and surface studies. He is a member of "Investigadoras e Investigadores por México" in CONACYT, having been assigned from 2016 to 2022 to the University of Guadalajara at CUCEI, and since 2022 to the present at the Universidad Politécnica del Valle de México- Tultitlán (UPVM). He has extensive experience in the study, modification, and application of surfaces, including establishing a laboratory at UPVM dedicated to modifying and studying surface properties. He has designed and built several tribometers with sliding contact configurations. Similarly, he has experience in surface modification, including the deposition of metallic, ceramic, polymeric, and composite films on various material substrates using physical and chemical techniques. Currently, he is involved in several projects aimed at improving the tribological properties used in the medical, energy, and food industries.

Dr. Maximiliano Rossa carried out under-graduate and doctoral studies at the Facultad de Ciencias Químicas of the Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, earning a Ph.D. in Chemical Sciences in 2005. He held post-doctoral positions at INFIQC (Córdoba, Argentina) in 2007-2009, and at the Laboratoire de Chimie Physique/Université Paris-Sud 11 (Orsay, France) in 2010. As well, he performed short research stays at the Departamento de Química Física I/Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain) in 2008, and jointly at the Centre Laser Infrarouge d'Orsay (France) and at the Centre Physique des Interactions Ioniques et Moléculaires/Université Aix-Marseille (France) in 2017 and 2019. His main research field is Physical Chemistry, with focus on Molecular Reaction Dynamics for studying a variety of gas-phase physical and chemical processes (involving metal-containing species and clusters, as well as s-heptazine derivatives), and on Laser Chemistry, especially in pulsed laser ablation/desorption of solids and its applications to laser processing of (bio)materials.

Dr. McCullough is an internist, cardiologist, epidemiologist holding degrees from Baylor University, University of Texas Southwestern Medical School, University of Michigan, and Southern Methodist University. He manages common infectious diseases as well as the cardiovascular complications of both the viral infection and the injuries developing after the COVID-19 vaccine in Dallas TX, USA. Dr. McCullough has broadly published on a range of topics in medicine with > 1000 publications and > 685 citations in the National Library of Medicine. His works include "Pathophysiological Basis and Rationale for Early Outpatient Treatment of SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) Infection" the first widely utilized treatment regimen for ambulatory patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 in the American Journal of Medicine and subsequently updated in Reviews in Cardiovascular Medicine. Subsequently he published the first detoxification approach titled "Clinical Rationale for SARS-CoV-2 Base Spike Protein Detoxification in Post COVID-19 and Vaccine Injury Syndromes" in the Journal of American Physicians and Surgeons. He has dozens of peer-reviewed publications on the infection and has commented extensively on the medical response to the COVID-19 crisis in TheHill, America Out Loud, and on FOX NEWS Channel. Dr. McCullough testified multiple times in the US Senate, European Parliament, Texas Senate Committee on Health and Human Services, Arizona Senate and House of Representatives, Colorado General Assembly, New Hampshire Senate, Pennsylvania Senate, and South Carolina Senate concerning many aspects of the pandemic response. Dr. McCullough has had years of dedicated academic and clinical efforts in combating the SARS-CoV-2 virus and in doing so, has reviewed thousands of reports, participated in scientific congresses, group discussions, press releases, and has been considered among the world's experts on COVID-19.

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